
Temperate and boreal primeval forests in the face of global change

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Program and Abstracts

Disturbances and renewal in primeval and managed forests

Impact of forest development phases on soil C and N stocks: insufficient and controversial data

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Soil organic matter is one of the biggest carbon stocks on the planet. The stability of soil organic matter depends on many factors, but one of the most important is the availability of nitrogen. Therefore it is recommended to study C and N stocks simultaneously. There is still insufficient data about the distribution of soil organic matter and belowground biomass in forests. In this study, we evaluated the content of total organic carbon and total nitrogen in Dystric Cambisols of Uholka-Shyrokyi Luh primeval beech forest for each forest development phase (FDP). The classification approach and protocol of Zenner et al. (2016) were used to identify FDPs. All the studies were conducted in three replicates – three separate locations for each FDP. We analyzed the content of carbon and nitrogen in the topsoil (0 – 10 cm) with CHN analyzer. The hypothesis was that FDP affects soil properties and in particular content of C and N. We thought that content of these elements in the soil would depend on the FDP and thus may be used as an additional criterion for the identification of the phase. Unfortunately, the dispersion of C and N contents in the group (different sites under the one type of development phase) was almost the same as between the groups (different development phases). Our results contradict with previously published data (Henyk, 2011) that showed significant differences in C content in soils under different FDPs. We conclude that i) content of C and N in the studied soils was not a sensitive indicator of the FDP; ii) this may be explained by statistical noise and other inaccuracies, caused by significant spatial heterogeneity of soil properties iii) in future studies should be more replicates and Kalman filtering or equivalent should be applied to the raw data.